

ID _____

Please provide your answer in the boxes provided, or tick yes or no

1. Please tick which reminder you received

- Reminder from a GP or practice nurse about retinopathy screening in person when I attended for an appointment
- Phone call from a practice nurse reminding me about retinopathy screening
- Letter from the practice with an information leaflet about retinopathy screening

2. What is your age?

- 18–30 years
- 31–44 years
- 45-64 years
- 65-79 years
- 80 years or more

3. What type of diabetes do you have?

- Type 1
- Type 2
- Unsure

4. How long have you had diabetes?

- Less than 12 months
- 1–5 years
- 6- 10 years
- Over 10 years
- Unsure

5. What is your employment status?

- Full-time employed
- Part-time employed
- Self-employed or working for family business
- Unemployed
- Education including vocational training or retraining
- Maternity or paternity leave
- Retired
- Permanent sick or disabled
- Looking after home or family

Other, please specify

6. **Do you have a family member with diabetes?** Yes No

7. **Do you have any existing diabetes-related complication(s), or have you had any in the past?**

Yes No

If yes, please tick which complications

- Leg ulcers
- Protein in your urine
- Lack of feeling and tingling pain in your legs and feet due to nerve damage (diabetic neuropathy)
- Damage to the back of your eye (diabetic retinopathy)
- Damage to your kidneys (diabetic nephropathy)
- Cardiovascular problems (e.g. heart attack, stroke, angina)

Other, please specify